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THE INFLUENCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND INTELLECTUAL INTELLIGENCE ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE THROUGH ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE

ВПЛИВ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЙНОЇ КУЛЬТУРИ ТА ІНТЕЛЕКТУАЛЬНОГО ІНТЕЛЕКТУ НА ПРОДУКТИВНІСТЬ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ ЧЕРЕЗ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЙНУ ГРОМАДЯНСЬКУ ПОВЕДІНКУ ЯК ПРОМІЖНУ ЗМІННУ

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Фітра Нур Джанні Насутіон, Сайфуддін, Салман Фаріс, Пурнама Янті Пурба. Вплив організаційної культури та інтелектуального інтелекту на продуктивність працівників через організаційну громадянську поведінку як проміжну змінну. Науково-методична стаття.

Це дослідження має на меті вивчити вплив організаційної культури та інтелектуального інтелекту на ефективність роботи через організаційну громадянську поведінку серед співробітників Регіонального підрозділу поліції державної служби в регентстві Лабуханбату. У дослідженні взяли участь 73 постійні співробітники (державні службовці) Регіонального підрозділу поліції державної служби в регентстві Лабуханбату. Для збору даних використовувалися анкетування та документальні дослідження. Аналіз даних проводився за допомогою SPSS версії 25, включаючи t-тести, тести Собела та шляховий аналіз. Результати свідчать про значний позитивний вплив організаційної культури та інтелектуального інтелекту на громадянську поведінку та ефективність організації. Крім того, громадянська поведінка організації опосередковує зв'язок між організаційною культурою та інтелектуальним інтелектом і результативністю.

Ключові слова: організаційна культура, інтелектуальний інтелект, ефективність, громадянська поведінка організації

Fitra Nur Janni Nasution, Syaifuddin, Salman Faris, Purnama Yanti Purba. The Influence of Organizational Culture and Intellectual Intelligence on Employee Performance Through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an Intervening Variable. Scientific and methodical article.

This research aims to examine the influence of Organizational Culture and Intellectual Intelligence on Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior among employees of the Regional Civil Service Police Unit in Labuhanbatu Regency. The study involved 73 permanent employees (Civil Servants) of the Regional Civil Service Police Unit in Labuhanbatu Regency. Data collection utilized questionnaires and documentary studies. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25, including t-tests, Sobel tests, and path analysis. The results indicate a significant positive influence of Organizational Culture and Intellectual Intelligence on Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Performance. Furthermore, Organizational Citizenship Behavior mediates the relationship between Organizational Culture and Intellectual Intelligence with Performance.

Keywords: organizational culture, intellectual intelligence, performance, organizational citizenship behavior

Human resources play a crucial role in a company's operations. The success of a company in achieving its goals is influenced by its human resources or employees who carry out their tasks. Every company strives to acquire high-quality human resources; the low quality of human resources can have adverse effects on the company (organization). Therefore, companies need to manage human resources effectively to achieve their goals, enabling the organization to achieve its objectives efficiently and effectively while also ensuring its continued survival and growth.

In organisations, the human resource factor is the main problem in every activity in it because if the human resources in the organisation are bad, then the objectives of the organisation cannot be achieved as planned, because the role of human resources in the organisation is to determine the success of the organisation. All actions taken in every activity are initiated and determined by humans who are members of an organisation. In organisations, it is definitely very necessary to have a potential human resource factor, both leaders and employees in the pattern of tasks and supervision which is a determinant for the achievement of the organisation's goals.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Based on the preliminary research conducted on the employees of the Regional Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency, phenomena were found, one of which is the insufficient OCB behavior. This was revealed through initial interviews with the head of the Regional Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency, who mentioned that many employees only show enthusiasm within the confines of their job descriptions (in-role), without being willing to take on extra-role responsibilities, assuming that fulfilling their assigned tasks and duties is sufficient. If they do agree to work extra, it is typically motivated by expectations of rewards or recognition. Conversely, if their expectations are not met, they tend to work half-heartedly due to a sense of coercion. One of the internal factors that can shape OCB, among the most important, is job satisfaction, which is a significant determinant of OCB behavior (Robbins and Judge, 2015). With job satisfaction attained by employees, organizations anticipate positive behavior such as OCB to enhance organizational productivity, surpassing normal job expectations. Organizations stand to benefit more when employees exhibit voluntary behaviors and exceed role demands (Titisari, 2014).

Based on the phenomenon that occurred in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency, the researcher is interested in conducting a study related to this phenomenon with the title "The Influence of Organizational Culture and Intellectual Intelligence on Employee Performance Through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an Intervening Variable in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency".

The main part

Performance is about the results of a series of tasks accomplished over a specific period of time and can be measured in terms of both quality and quantity with the aim of assessing the alignment of work with the goals intended to be achieved within the organization. Here are the performance assessment indicators:

1. Quantity of work output.
2. Quality of work output.
3. Efficiency.
4. Work discipline.
5. Initiative.
6. Accuracy.
7. Leadership.
8. Honesty.
9. Creativity.

Organizational culture is a system that contains norms, beliefs, values, and habits that are established, agreed upon, serve as guidelines, and are followed by its members. It includes:

1. Innovative risk-taking.
2. Outcome orientation.
3. Employee focus.
4. Attention to detail in task orientation.

Intellectual intelligence is the capacity or ability to think relying on reason and logic, which is used to understand something. The following are indicators of intellectual intelligence assessment:

1. Numerical intelligence.
2. Verbal intelligence.
3. Perceptual speed.
4. Inductive reasoning.
5. Deductive reasoning.
6. Spatial visualization.
7. Memory capacity.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) is an extra-role behavior or contribution in which the actions taken are not actually mandatory or obligatory but rather a form of employee discretion that provides benefits without expecting any compensation. Here are the indicators for assessing Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB):

1. Altruism.
2. Courtesy.
3. Sportsmanship.
4. Conscientiousness.
5. Civic virtue.

RESULT. This research employs data analysis techniques using quantitative data processed with SPSS version 25 software, t-test, Sobel test, and path analysis.

Respondent Characteristics. The majority of respondents were 41-50 years old with 30 employees (53.4%). While the number of respondents aged 20-30 years was 15 employees (27.4%), the number of respondents aged 31-40 was 16 employees (24.7%) and the number of respondents aged > 50 years was 12 employees (19.2%).

Table 1. Results of t-Test for Sub Model I

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26.833	1.872		14.334	.000
	organisational culture	.236	.076	.339	3.095	.003
	Intellectual Intelligence	.104	.049	.234	2.141	.036

a. Dependent Variable: *Organizational Citizenship Behavior*

Source: authors' own elaboration

In the table, the t-test statistic was obtained as follows:

1. The Organizational Culture variable (X1) yielded a t-value (3.095) > the critical t-value (1.99) at a significance level (Sig) of 0.003 (< 0.05). This indicates that Organizational Culture significantly influences the Organizational Citizenship Behavior variable.

2. The Intellectual Intelligence variable (X2) yielded a t-value (2.141) > the critical t-value (1.99) at a significance level (Sig) of 0.036 (< 0.05). This indicates that Intellectual Intelligence significantly influences the Organizational Citizenship Behavior variable.

Thus the path analysis equation can be arranged as follows:

$$Z = 21.492 + 0.071X1 + 0.050X2$$

The analysis equation model means:

1) The constant value is 21.492 which means that if the independent variables, namely Leadership (X1) and Supervision (X2) are equal to zero, then Motivation (Z) is 21.492.

2) The regression coefficient value X1 = 0.071 indicates that if Leadership increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 7.1%.

3) The regression coefficient value X2 = 0.050 shows that if Supervision increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 5%.

Table 2. Summary of Model Testing Results for Sub-Model I

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.403 ^a	.163	.139	1.041

Source: authors' own elaboration

The data above indicates that the contribution or influence of the variables Organizational Culture (X1) and Intellectual Intelligence (X2) on the variable Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z) is 13.9%, while the remaining 86.1% is the contribution from other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, for the value of ϵ_1 can be found using the formula $\epsilon_1 = \sqrt{1-0.139} = 0.9279$.

Table 3. Results of t-Test for Sub Model II

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	19.022	3.419		5.563	.000
	organisational culture	.060	.075	.027	2.270	.008
	Intellectual Intelligence	.267	.046	.555	5.781	.000
	<i>Organizational Citizenship Behavior</i>	.478	.110	.441	4.341	.000

a. Dependent Variable: *Kinerja*

Source: authors' own elaboration

In the table, the t-test statistic was obtained as follows:

1. The variable Organizational Culture (X1) with a t-value of (2.270) > t-table (1.99) at a significance level (Sig) of 0.008 (< 0.05).

2. This indicates that Organizational Culture significantly influences Performance. The variable Intellectual Intelligence (X2) with a t-value of (5.781) > t-table (1.99) at a significance level (Sig) of 0.000 (< 0.05).

3. This indicates that Intellectual Intelligence significantly influences Performance.

4. The variable Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z) with a t-value of (4.341) > t-table (1.99) at a significance level (Sig) of 0.000 (< 0.05). This indicates that Organizational Citizenship Behavior significantly influences Performance.

Table 4. Summary of Model Testing Results for Sub-Model II

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.636	.405	.379	.959

Source: authors' own elaboration

The data above indicates that the contribution or influence of the variables Organizational Culture (X1), Intellectual Intelligence (X2), and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Z) on the variable Performance (Y) is 37.9%, while the remaining 61.2% is contributed by other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, for the value of ϵ_1 can be calculated using the formula $\epsilon_1 = \sqrt{1-0.379} = 0.7880$.

Table 5. Results of t-Test for Sub Model II

Variabel	Unstandardized	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Std. Error	P-Value
Organisational Culture on Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.283 (a)	0.138 (S _a)	1.139	0.051	0.254
Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Performance	0.207 (b)	0.151 (S _b)			
Intellectual Intelligence on Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.102 (a)	0.090 (S _a)	0.965	0.028	0.334
Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Performance	0.265 (b)	0.144 (S _b)			

Source: authors' own elaboration

The test statistic value for the influence of Organizational Culture on Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an intervening variable has a test statistic value of $1.139 < 1.96$ with a significance of $0.254 > 0.05$, meaning Hypothesis 6 is not accepted, indicating that Organizational Citizenship Behavior is not able to mediate the influence of Organizational Culture on Performance. The test statistic value for the influence of Intellectual Intelligence on Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an intervening variable has a test statistic value of $0.965 < 1.96$ with a significance of $0.334 > 0.05$, meaning Hypothesis 7 is not accepted, indicating that Organizational Citizenship Behavior is not able to mediate the influence of Intellectual Intelligence on Performance.

The Influence of Leadership on Motivation. The Leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on Motivation in the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. The Leadership variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.071, indicating that if Leadership increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 7.1%.

Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Leadership has a significant influence on the Motivation of the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit.

The influence of supervision on motivation. The Supervision variable has a positive and significant effect on Motivation in the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. The Supervision variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.050, indicating that if Supervision increases by 100%, it will increase Motivation by 5%.

Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Supervision has a significant influence on the Motivation of the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit.

The Influence of Leadership on Performance. The Leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. The leadership variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.212, indicating that if leadership increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 21.2%.

Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Leadership has a significant influence on the Performance of the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit.

The influence of supervision on performance. The Supervision variable has a positive and significant effect on performance in the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. The Supervision variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.288, indicating that if supervision increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 28.8%.

Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Supervision has a significant effect on the Performance of the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. This is supported by research conducted by Manda Amelia Nawawi (2022) with the title The Effect of Supervision on Employee Performance (Study at the Central Lampung Regency Bina Marga Office), Ahmad Rivai (2021) with the title The Effect of Supervision, Discipline and Motivation on Teacher Performance, Dwiki Ramdani, Darmawaty Abd. Razak, and Sandi Prahara (2023) with the title The Effect of Supervision on the Performance of Aviation Security Employees at Djalaluddin Gorontalo Airport.

The Influence of Motivation on Performance. Motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on performance in the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. The motivation variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.350, indicating that if motivation increases by 100%, it will increase performance by 35%.

Based on the results of testing the first hypothesis, it is known that Motivation has a significant influence on the Performance of the Labuhanbatu Civil Service Police Unit. This is supported by research conducted by Jimmy Hansen Manalu (2019) with the title *The Effect of Motivation and Training on Employee Performance at PT. Gutji Swarnadwipa Medan Branch*, Tifani Nur Adinda, Muhamad Azis Firdaus, and Syahrums Agung (2023) with the title *The Effect of Work Motivation and Work Discipline on Employee Performance*, Bukhari, Sjahril Effendi Pasaribu (2019) with the title *The Effect of Motivation, Competence, and Work Environment on Performance*.

Conclusions

Based on the research results and discussions conducted by researchers regarding the influence of Organizational Culture and Intellectual Intelligence on employee performance in the Civil Service Police Unit through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an intervening variable, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Organizational Culture influences Organizational Citizenship Behavior in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.
2. Intellectual Intelligence influences Organizational Citizenship Behavior in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.
3. Organizational Culture influences Performance in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.
4. Intellectual Intelligence influences Performance in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.
5. Organizational Citizenship Behavior influences Performance in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency.
6. Organizational Culture influences Performance in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an intervening variable.
7. Intellectual Intelligence influences Performance in the Civil Service Police Unit of Labuhanbatu Regency through Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an intervening variable

Suggestions.

1. The Labuhanbatu District Civil Service Police Unit should pay attention to employees in completing tasks with quality results and achieving targets.
2. The Labuhanbatu District Civil Service Police Unit should pay attention to employees who have meticulous abilities in performing tasks and are capable of creating accurate work results.
3. The Labuhanbatu District Civil Service Police Unit should pay attention to employees who have the ability to quickly and accurately recognize visual similarities and differences.
4. The Labuhanbatu District Civil Service Police Unit should pay attention to employees who have a sportsmanlike attitude in their work and can tolerate less than ideal work situations.

Abstract

This research aims to examine the influence of Organizational Culture and Intellectual Intelligence on Performance through Organizational Citizenship Behavior among employees of the Regional Civil Service Police Unit in Labuhanbatu Regency. The study involved 73 permanent employees (Civil Servants) of the Regional Civil Service Police Unit in Labuhanbatu Regency. Data collection utilized questionnaires and documentary studies. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25, including t-tests, Sobel tests, and path analysis. The results indicate a significant positive influence of Organizational Culture and Intellectual Intelligence on Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Performance. Furthermore, Organizational Citizenship Behavior mediates the relationship between Organizational Culture and Intellectual Intelligence with Performance.

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